

Supplemental Figure 3

SI Figure 3: *Cdh1* mRNA expression initiated by HDE. Expression of *Cdh1*, a gene encoding E-cadherin, was examined in intestinal epithelial cell by qPCR. *Cdh1* mRNA expression was unaltered in the ileum (unpaired t-test, $p=0.1255$; $n=5-6$), cecum (unpaired t-test, $p=0.1135$; $n=6$), proximal colon (unpaired t-test, $p=0.9307$; $n=5-6$), distal colon (unpaired t-test, $p=0.3290$; $n=5$). The sex of each mouse is depicted by the data point color (light/pink (female) or light/blue (male)).